

Norwich Papers

STUDIES IN TRANSLATION
Volume 18 November 2010

Written Out: Translating Exclusion

Norwich Papers is an annual journal based at the University of East Anglia which publishes a range of essays on issues in Translation Studies. Each edition concentrates on a specific theme and gathers papers from a wide range of contributors. Recent titles include *Translation / Transculture*, *Experiments in Translation*; *The Translator as Writer* and *Identities: The Role of Translation in Global and National Contexts*.

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Norwich Papers 2010

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Printed and bound by The Print Group, University of East Anglia, Norwich, NR4 7TJ, United Kingdom.

ISSN 0964-3419

Norwich Papers

Written Out: Translating Exclusion

Editorial Note

The idea behind this issue, *Written Out: Translating Exclusion*, was to invite our contributors to consider all aspects of exclusion in translation, be it the translation of minority perspectives, from or into minority languages, in difficult political situations, or, from a linguistic perspective, the omission of certain aspects of the source text in a translated text, and its effects.

As you read through the papers in this issue you will see that our contributors have amply met this challenge, writing compelling papers on many different occurrences of exclusion in the world of translation. We hope that it will set your minds to work, and that you in turn will be inspired to look into issues of inclusivity and exclusivity in your future translation work.

This year Norwich Papers has a new logo and a new look. Somewhat ironically, this is going to make it stand out of the crowd and exclude it from the visual set of Norwich Papers that currently adorns your bookshelf. But we hope it will not spoil your enjoyment of what we have found to be an exciting and innovative set of papers on the realities of translation today.

The Norwich Papers Team
Norwich, November 2010

Acknowledgements

The editorial team would like to thank Prof. Jean Boase-Beier (Managing Editor) for her continuing support, and all those in the School of Literature and Creative Writing and in the Print Group who have helped the team during the course of the year. Particular thanks go to our graphic designer, to Nicola Talbot for her IT training, and to Antoinette Fawcett, without whose assistance we quite simply could not have published this issue.

CONTENTS

Notes On Contributors	i
Introduction <i>Jean Boase-Beier</i>	iii
OBERIU and the pitfalls of translating Russian absurdism <i>Katie Kahle</i>	1
Translating cultures, negotiating differences. The construction and representation of identities in the postcolonial context <i>Elena Rodriguez Murphy</i>	19
The Psychological Travail of the Translator: Derrida's Methodology in Translation Studies <i>Maziyar Faridi</i>	33
Ignoring the Other: The exclusion of interpreters in the Spanish dubbing of <i>It's a Free World...</i> <i>Irene de-Higes-Andino</i>	50
Translating Baffo's Erotic Sonnets; or the Joys of Molesting the Text <i>Daniela Almansi</i>	69
'In the Name of the Law': manipulation and censorship in <i>Gomorra</i> <i>Maria Cristina Consiglio</i>	81
Judging omissions of legal language in translated legal fiction <i>Maria Paz Marin-Garcia</i>	96
Translation as Peaceable Resistance <i>Corine Tachtiris</i>	115
Inclusion and exclusion in literary translation: the strange case of Carlo Emilio Gadda in English translation <i>Cristina Olivari</i>	127
Translating St. Anthony – some reflections on a new type of censorship that translators into German have been confronted with in recent years <i>Gabriele Haefs</i>	143

Judging omissions of legal language in translated legal fiction

Maria Paz Marín-García

Introduction

This paper deals with the exclusion of cultural references in translation, specifically, cultural referents that appear in English language legal-fiction literature and its translations into peninsular Spanish. In order to discard exclusions which are related to political censorship or to issues of discrimination in the target culture, the translations studied were made between 2004 and 2006. Two main possibilities for exclusion (or omission) are initially considered. The first one is the lack of an equivalent due to differences between the two legal systems in contact through the translation. The second one would be the abuse of redundancies by the authors themselves with the translators deciding not to reproduce such redundancies, probably for stylistic reasons in the receiving culture. Our experimental work will aim to confirm whether these hypotheses are right and, if not, what other possibilities there might be.

Cultural referents

Techniques applied to the translation of cultural referents are the main focus of this paper; for this reason, a brief review of the different names given to cultural elements that can be identified as specific of a given culture is first given, before the actual research is discussed. There is agreement that these elements constitute one of the main sources of translation problems since cultural referents refer to elements specific to a given culture. Nevertheless, several terms are used to designate such features.

The term *realia* is used by Kade (1964 and 1968), Vlahov and Florin (1970), Bödeker and Fresse (1987) and Koller (1992). Nida, on the other hand, prefers the terms *cultural elements* (Nida 1945) or *cultural features* (Nida 1964), whilst following Nida's proposal, Newmark categorises 'foreign cultural words' and refers to them as *cultural terms* (1988: 94-95, 1991: 141). Other terms used in recent years are *culture bound lexis* (Katan 1999) and *allusions* (Leppihalme 1997), whereas

amongst functionalists, the name preferred is *cultureme* as used by Vermeer (1983), Oksaar (1988) and Nord (1997), although Nord (1994) has also used *culture-marker*.

Moreover, the terminology used among Spanish scholars is also very varied. We can find: *cultural referents* (Mayoral 1994, 1999/2000; used to refer to objects), *culture-specific items* (Franco 1996), *culturally marked textual segments* (Mayoral and Muñoz 1997, used for referring to signs, not to objects), *specific cultural referents* (Cartagena 1998), *specific cultural markers* (Herrero 2000: 311), and *cultureme* (Molina, 2006: 77, following the functionalist tradition), whereas Marco (2002: 205), following the School of Granada, uses the term *cultural referent*. This is the term that that will be used in this paper.

Technique and translation technique

Since this paper is going to deal with cases of omission technique in the translation of cultural referents, I will briefly review the concepts of technique and translation technique.

There is a wide variety of terminology used to refer to the same concept, and, some of the terms are used with different meanings. For example, we use 'technique' in the same sense as Fawcett (1997), Hurtado (2001), Molina and Hurtado (2002), and Marco (2002 and 2004), meanwhile other authors show a preference for: 'procedures' (Vinay and Darbelent 1958; Newmark 1988 –although he also uses 'technique'), 'techniques of adjustment' (Nida 1964), 'shifts' (Catford 1965), 'transfer operation' (Klaudy 2003) or 'strategies' (Chesterman 2005). As Marco (2007: 255) points out, some terminological uses and some factors are strongly linked to different national traditions or may be linked to school affiliations. For this reason, we consider it important to delineate this concept. Molina and Hurtado have done relevant research on this topic and we will follow them. For Molina and Hurtado (2002: 506) the terminological confusions were started by Vinay and Darbelnet, since these authors followed the traditional methodological dichotomy, literal translation/free translation, and arranged procedures accordingly. Molina and Hurtado (2002: 506) consider that a translation technique 'describes the result and affects smaller sections of the

translation'; consequently, they define translation techniques as 'procedures to analyse and classify how translation equivalence works' (2002: 509).

Some of the most well-known classifications of translation techniques are the ones proposed by Vinay and Darbelnet (1958: 46-55) and Newmark (1988: 81-83), based on Vinay and Darbelnet's. Also Molina and Hurtado (2002: 509-510) offer a classification of 18 translation techniques. All these proposals are 'general', that is, they do not distinguish with regard to specific translation problems. Some authors apply a general proposal of techniques even when their research deals with specific translation problems; such is the case of Molina (2006) and her study of cultural referents. However, as Marco (2004: 137) points out, there are authors who consider techniques according to a given translation problem such as translation of metaphor (Toury 1995) or plays with words (Delabastita 1996).

Techniques for the translation of cultural referents

In this section I briefly revisit authors that specify techniques for the translation of cultural referents, that is: Newmark (1988), Franco (1996) and Marco (2002, 2004).

Newmark (1988: 81-93) sets forth a typology of translation procedures based on Vinay and Darbelnet's classical proposal. Newmark, in his 1988 work, dedicates one chapter exclusively to the topic of translation and culture, where he proposes 12 techniques, although he calls them 'procedures', to be applied when dealing with the translation of cultural elements. Another author that also studies techniques for the translation of cultural referents is Franco (1996), by which he aims to show the cultural manipulation in translation and also the degree to which this occurs (1996: 60, 71). Following Newmark, Marco (2004: 137-139) presents a new proposal of only 9 categories since he considers some Newmark's categories are redundant. Based on this taxonomy, we offer our proposal of techniques in which we add one more category, which we call synonymy and which is understood in its broadest sense. This proposal is presented here:

Borrowing	This is the inclusion of one word of expression of another language without changing it.
Literal translation	This involves translating word for word a syntagm or expression.
Neutralization	Following Newmark, it involves the explanation of the cultural referent with words that refer to its function or external characteristics.
Amplification	The translator adds information to the cultural referent; it can be done through explicitness, paraphrase, etc.
Compression	This is when the translator synthesizes linguistic elements; usually when the cultural referent is known in the target culture but not in the source culture.
Adaptation	This is 'use of concept in the target culture that is approximately equivalent to the original', when the original does not exist in the target culture.
Coined equivalent	It involves the use of a term or expression well-known (it is in the dictionary, it is used by people) as an equivalent in the target language.
Omission	This is the deletion of elements considered redundant or of little importance.
Creation	It involves the introduction of a cultural referent where there was none in the original text.
Synonymy	It is considered in its broadest sense. It includes figures such as metonymy, synecdoche, hyperonym, hyponym.

Finally, I should point out that, for the purposes of this research, omission includes not only the complete disappearance of the cultural referent in the target text, but also the few cases where the term in the source text has been eliminated in the target text but some reference to it is kept through the use of a pronoun or proper name, neither being a cultural referent. This has been done to keep achieve consistency with the technique of creation, which includes both creation 'from zero' and creation from a non cultural referent.

Corpus

These techniques are investigated within our corpus, which was obtained from three novels written in English with an American context and from their translation into peninsular Spanish. The three novels are *To Kill a Mockingbird* by Harper Lee, *The Last Juror* by John Grisham and *Sons of Fortune* by Jeffrey Archer. The common link among these works is legal fiction. Particularly, the three works portray a criminal trial with jury, which is crucial within the story told. Also, they deal with similar crimes: rape in *To Kill a Mockingbird*, murder and rape in *The Last Juror*, and murder in *Sons of Fortune*. These three works also share aspects pointed out as characteristic in legal fiction by the American movement *Law and Literature*, such as the explanation of the jury trial or the treatment of the jury: its critics, gender or racial prejudices, description of its members, lack of interest to be a juror, jurors being threatened, etc. The fact that the first work belongs to high literature and the other two to popular culture does not affect our research or our results, since only cultural referents related to the criminal process are analysed.

Analysis of data and results

The corpus consists of nearly 3,000 examples, including repetitions, of cultural referents which have been analysed applying our proposal of techniques for cultural referents we have explained above. This paper only deals with the results of the investigation of the technique of omission. Within this corpus, we can see that this technique has only been used on 97 occasions, and that just 49 cultural referents that appeared in the source texts have been excluded in the translations. If we have a closer look by translator (see *Table 1*), we observe that Archer's translator uses this technique 40 times, out of 963 cultural referents used by Archer, or 3.9% of all techniques used (total of 1,009). The difference between the number of cultural referents used by the author and the number of cultural referents used by the translator is easy to explain. Translators not only apply techniques to deal with the cultural referents used by the author, but have also used another technique – creation –, by which they introduce cultural referents that were not in the original text. This means that the total of techniques used by translators will be a bit higher than the total of

cultural referents used by authors, since the count of translators' techniques include both omissions and creations, together with all the other techniques.

With regard to Lee, we can see her translator used this technique 41 times, nearly as much as Archer's. However, Lee's use of cultural referents (636) is nearly half of Grisham's (1,205). This means, that in the total of Lee's work, her translator uses this technique 6.1% (with respect to the 675 translation techniques used). On the other hand, we can observe that Grisham, the only author with a legal background, is the one who used more cultural referents in his work and whose translator used the technique of omission less, only 16 times out of 1,205 cultural referents used by the author. This is a mere 1.3% frequency of all the cultural referents (1,246) used by his translator.

Technique	Archer's translator	Grisham's translator	Lee's translator	Total general	Archer's translator	Grisham's translator	Lee's translator
Omission	39	16	41	96	3.9%	1.3%	6.1%
Cultural referents by translator	1009	1246	675	2930			
Cultural referents by author	963	1205	636	2704			

Table 1. Frequency of omission technique by translator

Table 2 shows the cultural referents excluded, together with the number of exclusions with regard to that cultural referent by each translator, and the frequency of use of that cultural referent by authors. Finally, the last column refers to the total use of those cultural referents in the corpus. This table is arranged in descending order according to frequency in the total of the corpus. We can see that the first 30 cultural referents appear from 6 to 236 times in the corpus. This includes 22 cultural referents which have been used by all 3 authors, plus another 8 only used by one or two of the authors. The remaining 19 cultural referents appear 5 or fewer times in the total of the corpus and only one or two of the authors have used that cultural referent.

Term	Omissions by Translators						Corpus
	Archer			Grisham		Lee	
	A	G	L	Total A	Total G	Total L	
judge	4	0	12	82	45	109	236
jury	1	1	3	61	45	57	163
witness	1	0	4	20	23	36	79
court	10	0	1	34	11	29	74
courtroom	3	1	0	19	18	25	62
case	1	1	1	22	20	9	51
trial	0	2	0	15	29	4	48
murder	1	1	0	25	21	1	47
state (noun)	1	0	1	18	20	5	43
juror	1	1	--	7	34	0	41
evidence	2	0	1	18	7	11	36
defendant	1	0	1	11	8	14	33
witness stand	0	0	1	13	3	11	27
defence	0	0	1	5	17	3	25
crime	1	0	0	9	13	2	24
testified	--	1	0	0	13	6	19
law	0	0	1	2	7	7	16
bailiff	--	1	--	0	13	0	13
bench	1	0	1	2	4	7	13
stand	0	0	1	2	4	7	13
board	--	1	--	0	11	0	11
counsellor	1	--	--	10	0	0	10
hung jury	1	0	0	3	5	1	9
court reporter	--	0	1	0	1	7	8
cross-examination	0	1	0	2	2	4	8
detective	1	--	--	7	0	0	7
excused	--	1	1	0	4	3	7
prosecutor	1	0	0	1	5	1	7
charged	1	0	0	3	2	1	6
proceeding	0	0	1	2	2	2	6
offence	--	0	1	0	1	4	5
chief	1	--	--	3	0	0	3
handcuffs	--	1	--	0	3	0	3
law-abiding	0	1	--	1	2	0	3
print	1	--	--	3	0	0	3
reporter	--	--	1	0	0	3	3
irrelevant or immaterial	--	--	1	0	0	2	2
reasonable doubt	--	0	1	0	1	1	2
stated (verb)	1	0	--	1	1	0	2
well of the court	1	--	--	2	0	0	2
called the court to order	1	--	--	1	0	0	1
come before me	--	--	1	0	0	1	1
county solicitor	--	--	1	0	0	1	1
for the court	--	1	--	0	1	0	1

in open court	--	--	1	0	0	1	1
incarceration	--	1	--	0	1	0	1
judicially	1	--	--	1	0	0	1
officers of the court	--	--	1	0	0	1	1
see the law	--	--	1	0	0	1	1
total	39	16	41	405	397	377	

Table 2. Relation between cultural referents, omissions and total appearance, by descendent frequency in corpus.

Now, if we have a closer look at these data, we can observe that only a few cultural referents have been omitted more than once by the translators. For example, *judge* has been omitted 12 times out of the 109 times used by Lee, and 4 times out of the 82 used by Archer. In the case of Lee, the source text (see Table 3) refers to *judge*, in 10 occasions as 'judge Taylor' (L73, L76, L99, L114, L126, L131, L141, L144, L150, L164) which can help to explain why the translator omitted the cultural referent, but kept the reference to him through his surname 6 times (L73, L114, L126, L141, L144, L164), another time the translation used a pronoun to keep the reference (L131) and the remaining three occasions the cultural referent was completely omitted (L76, L99, L150). Let's see them in their context, where *judge* is highlighted and 'Taylor' is both highlighted and marked in bold. When *judge* has been translated it has been marked as underlined in both columns (source text and translation). On the other hand, the four times of omissions of *judge* in Archer were complete omissions.

My ref	Pg ST	Source text	Pg TT	Translation
L73	176	So serene was Judge <1> Taylor's court<2>, that he had few occasions to use his gavel, but he hammered fully five minutes. [...]	252	Las audiencias <u>que presidía</u> <2> Taylor eran tan tranquilas que en pocas ocasiones tenía que utilizar el mazo, pero ahora estuvo golpeando un minuto largo. [...]
L76	177-178	'There has been a request<1>,' Judge <2> Taylor said, 'that this court-room be cleared of spectators <3>, or at least of women and children, a request<5> that will be denied<6> for the time being. [...]	253-254	—Se ha presentado la petición<1> de que la vista se celebre a <u>puertas cerradas</u> <3> —dijo entonces—, o al menos que la sala<4> se desaloje de mujeres y niños, una petición<5> que de momento se <u>deniega</u> <6>. [...]

L99	180	'All right, let's see,' said Judge<1> Taylor, 'but make sure we see, Atticus. Overruled<2>.'	257	—Está bien, veamos. Pero asegúrese de que lo veamos, Atticus. Protesta denegada<2>.
L106	181	'You're left-handed, Mr Ewell,' said Judge<1> Taylor. Mr Ewell turned angrily to the judge<2> and said he didn't see what his being left-handed had to do with it, that he was a Christ-fearing man [...].	258	—Usted es zurdo, señor Ewell —dijo el juez<1> Taylor. Ewell dijo que no veía qué tenía que ver el ser zurdo con lo que se discutía, que él era un hombre temeroso de Dios [...].
L114	183	Judge<1> Taylor cleared his throat and tried unsuccessfully to speak in soothing tones.	262	Taylor carraspeó para aclararse la voz y trató, aunque sin éxito, de hablar con tono apaciguador.
L126	186	Atticus resumed his stroll to the windows and let Judge<1> Taylor handle this one. Judge<2> Taylor was not the kind of figure that ever evoked pity, but I did feel a pang for him as he tried to explain.	265	Atticus reanudó el paseo hacia la ventana y el juez<1> Taylor se encargó de resolver el incidente. Taylor<2> no tenía una figura que moviese a compasión, a pesar de lo cual sentí pena por él, mientras trataba de explicar.
L127	186	The Judge<1> leaned back. 'Atticus, let's get on with these proceedings<2>, and let the record show<3> that the witness<4> has not been sassed, her views to the contrary.'	266	Y se reclinó en el sillón—. Adelante, Atticus, y que conste en acta<3> que nadie ha tratado con descaro a la testigo<4>.
L131	187	Mayella looked around, down at the court reporter<1>, up at the judge<2>. 'Answer the question, Miss Mayella,' said Judge<3> Taylor.	268	Mayella miró alrededor, bajó la vista hacia el taquígrafo<1> y la levantó hacia el juez<2>. —Responda a la pregunta, señorita Mayella —ordenó éste<3>.
L141	192	When Mr Gilmer told Judge<1> Taylor that the state<2> rested<3>, Judge<4> Taylor said:	274	Cuando Gilmer pidió al juez<1> un receso<3>, Taylor contestó:
L144	193	He distilled this for me to mean that Judge<1> Taylor might look lazy and operate in his sleep, but he was seldom reversed, and that was the proof of the pudding. Atticus said he was a good judge<2>.	274-275	Y me explicó 275 que esto significaba que por más que Taylor diese la sensación de perezoso y de adormilarse, raras veces dejaba sorprender. Atticus decía que Taylor era un buen juez<2>.
L150	193	'Shall we try to wind up this afternoon?' asked Judge<1> Taylor. 'How 'bout it, Atticus?'	275	¿Podremos dejarlo resuelto esta tarde? ¿Qué le parece Atticus?

L164	198	Darkness had not come, but the afternoon sun had left the windows. Judge<1> Taylor quickly restored order.	282	La oscuridad no había llegado todavía, pero el sol se había apartado de las ventanas. Taylor restableció rápidamente.
A146	205	'So I must now ask you Mr Stamp,' said the judge<1>, turning his attention back to the attorney general<2>, 'if it is your intention to apply for<3> a retrial<4> of this case<5>.'	216	Se dirigió al fiscal general<2> —. Debo preguntarle ahora, señor Stamp, si tiene usted la intención de solicitar<3> un nuevo juicio<4>.
A221	502	'Do you wish to respond, counsellor<1>?' asked the judge<2>, [...]	521	—¿Va usted a responder, abogado<1>? —preguntó, [...]
A222	502	Fletcher rose from his place and, looking directly at the judge<1>, said, 'No thank you, your honour<2>, it is not my intention to make an opening statement<4>.'	521	Fletcher se puso de pie y le respondió sin vacilar: —No, muchas gracias, señoría<2>. La defensa<3> no tiene la intención de hacer una exposición inicial<4>.
A347	518	Fletcher bowed to the judge<1>, stood up, walked over to the witness stand<2> and came to a halt in front of the detective<3>.	537	Fletcher agradeció la decisión con un gesto, se puso de pie y caminó hasta la tribuna de los testigos<2>, donde se detuvo delante del inspector<3>.

Table 3. Omissions of judge.

Another striking example is *court*, used by all the three authors a good number of times; Archer's translator does not translate it 10 times out of 34, whereas it has always been translated the 11 times that it appears in Grisham's novel and has been omitted only once in the 29 used by Lee. As we can see in Table 4, all these cases show a complete omission.

My ref	Pg ST	Source text	Pg TT	Translation
A44	175	'So we'll be spending our holiday in court<1> number three, will we?' asked Annie with a grin. 'It could even be court<2> number four,' said Fletcher,	186-187	—Por tanto, pasaremos las vacaciones en el juzgado<1> número tres, ¿no es así? —Annie sonrió. —Bien podría ser que nos tocara el número cuatro —contestó Fletcher

A97	198	Fletcher left the table, pushed open the little wooden gate dividing the court<1> from the public and strode quickly out of the courtroom<2> into the corridor.	209	Fletcher se levantó, abrió la portezuela de la barandilla que separaba a los asistentes y salió rápidamente de la sala<2>.
A147	205	The court's<1> attention swung to the state's lawyers<2>, all five of whom were in a huddle,	216	La atención de todos los presentes se centró en los cinco abogados del estado<2>, que mantenían una animada
A149	205	Cheering broke out in the well of the court<1> as the professor tore a sheet from his yellow pad and pushed it across to his pupil.	217	El público aplaudió con entusiasmo mientras el profesor arrancaba una hoja de su cuaderno y se la pasaba a su alumno.
A265	507	A little laughter broke out in the court<1> for a second time,	525	De nuevo se escucharon algunas risas dispersas
A348	518-519	'Were there any other fingerprints<1> in the gun?' 'There were partials of Mr Elliot's prints<2>, but they have been accounted for, remembering that he took the gun from his desk to protect himself.' 'But his prints<3> were on the gun' Laughter broke out in the court<4>.	537	—¿Había huellas dactilares<1> de alguien más en el arma? Había huellas<2> parciales del señor Elliot, pero estas están justificadas porque él cogió el arma del cajón para defenderse. —¿Las huellas<3> estaban en el arma? El público se echó a reír y Fletcher esperó a que cesaran las carcajadas
A372	523	'Mrs Elliot,' he<1> said quietly, as he stepped out into the well of the court<2>.	542	—Señora Elliot —dijo el fiscal<1> en voz baja, mientras se adelantaba—.
A375	524	[. . .] said the state's attorney<1> as he walked out into the well of the court<2> and across to the jury<3>.	543	[...] comentó el fiscal<1> mientras caminaba hacia el jurado<3>.
A383	527	Perhaps you would like me to ask the court<1> for an adjournment<2> so you have a little time to compose yourself?	546	¿Quiere que solicite un breve receso<2> para que pueda recuperarse?

A424	534	'Your honour<1>, I must. . . continued the state's attorney<2>, but he was interrupted by the court<3> doors being flung open	553	—Señoría<1>, debo... — insistió el fiscal<2>, pero se interrumpió al ver que se abría la puerta.
L75	177	In possession of his court<1> once more, Judge<2> Taylor leaned back in his chair.	253	Reinstaurado el orden, el juez<2> se reclinó en su sillón.

Table 4. Omissions of court.

Less significant are the cases of *witness*, *jury*, *courtroom*, *trial* and *evidence* (see Table 5), all of them used by the three authors. With regard to *witness*, Lee's translator has omitted it 4 times out of 36, Archer's translator only omitted it once out of 21, whereas Grisham's translator translated it all 23 times it appeared in the source text. *Jury* has been omitted by the three translators, once by Archer's, once by Grisham's and 3 times by Lee's. *Courtroom* has also been used by the three authors: Archer uses it 19 times and his translator omits its translation 3 times, Grisham uses it 18 times and his translator omits it once, and Lee uses it 25 times and all those are translated. *Trial* has been omitted twice by Grisham's translator out of the 29 cases in which he used it, and *evidence* has also been omitted twice out of 11 situations by Archer's translator and only once out of 11 by Lee's. We find, therefore, that translators have made a complete deletion of the cultural referent in nearly all these examples. In two cases (L182 and A452) the whole sentence was omitted instead of just the cultural referent. We can find only two situations with regard to *witness* where the translator has omitted the cultural referent but there is a reference to the concept through the use of a pronoun or proper name. These are just a few examples regarding a high frequency in the corpus.

If we move to the other extreme of the table, we can find examples of cultural referents that do not involve any terminological or cultural difficulty for the translator although they have been omitted, as it is the case of *reasonable doubt*, *incarceration* or *judicially*. The first one has only been used once by Grisham and Lee, and we can see Lee's translator decided to exclude it from its translation; similarly, the other two cultural referents appear only once in the whole corpus and their translators decided to suppress them.

My ref	Pg ST	Source text	Pg TT	Translation
		Witness		
L61	175	'That's m'name, cap'n,' said the witness<1>	250	—Ese es mi nombre, capitán — contestó él<1> con un acento horroroso.
L130	187	The witness<1> frowned as if puzzled. 'Friends?'	267	— ¿Amigos?
L181	201	The witness<1> realized his mistake and shifted uncomfortably in the chair	286	Tom <1> comprendió su error y se revolvió en la silla.
L182	202	To the next ten questions, as Mr Gilmer reviewed Mayella's version of events, the witness's<1> steady answer was that she was mistaken in her mind.		--
		Jury		
A67	186	The press have made great play of the fact that I did not object<1> to every white juror<2> who was selected; indeed there are ten of you on this jury<3>.	197	Los periódicos han mencionado hasta el cansancio que no he puesto objeción<1> alguna en la selección de los miembros<2> de raza blanca y, como se puede comprobar, son ustedes diez.
L24	168	One or two of the jury<1> looked vaguely like dressed-up Cunninghams.	239	Un par tenían un lejano aire de Cunningham bien vestidos; estaban sentados muy erguidos y atentos.
L166	198	'What did he say, Tom? You must tell the jury<1> what he said.	283	—¿Qué decía?
L242	215	A jury<1> ever looks at a defendant<2> it has convicted<3> and when this jury<4> came in, not one of them looked at Tom Robinson. [...].	307	Un jurado<1> nunca mira al acusado<2> al que acaba de condenar<3>, y ninguno de aquellos hombres miró a Tom Robinson. [...].
		Courtroom		
A120	203	When they reached the swing doors, the young counsellor<1> assumed his mentor would return to his place a couple of rows behind Annie and Jimmy, but he continued walking towards the front of the courtroom<2>.	214	Cuando llegaron a la barandilla, el joven supuso que su mentor ocuparía su asiento un par de filas detrás de Annie y Jimmy, pero no fue así sino que continuó para ir a sentarse junto a Fletcher.
A237	504	'First round to us, I think,' remarked Tom, as the state's team<1> hurriedly left	523	—Creo que hemos ganado el primer asalto —comentó Tom, mientras el

		the courtroom<2>.		fiscal_y los suyos<1> se retiraban apresuradamente.
A473	542	Whispering turned to chattering as everyone in the courtroom<1> began to discuss Rebecca's testimony<2>.	561	Los susurros se convirtieron en gritos mientras todos los presentes empezaban a comentar la revelación<2> de Rebecca.
G64	58	Wilbanks was gazing around the courtroom<1> as he continued, almost ignoring the Judge<2>, who, for the moment, seemed curious.	65	Wilbanks miró alrededor mientras seguía hablando casi sin prestar atención al juez<2>, que pareció sentir momentáneamente una cierta curiosidad.
		Trial		
G245	212	According to Baggy, a good trial<1> lawyer<2> never asks a question unless he knows the answer, especially with a witness<3> as dangerous as Malcolm Vince. Lucien was a good lawyer<4>, and he had no idea what Malcolm might blurt out.	213	Según Baggy, un buen abogado<2> jamás formula preguntas a menos que conozca la respuesta, sobre todo con un testigo<3> tan peligroso como Malcom Vince. Lucien era un buen abogado<4> y no tenía ni idea de lo que podía soltar
G286	226	This completes the guilt-or-innocence phase<1> of the trial<2>.	227	Con ello se da por finalizada la fase de determinación de la culpabilidad o la inocencia<1>.
		Evidence		
L108	182	A young girl walked to the witness stand<1>. As she raised her hand and swore that the evidence<2> she gave would be the truth, the whole truth, and nothing but the truth<3> > so help her God, she seemed somehow fragile-looking, but when she sat facing us in the witness chair<4> she became what she was, a thick-bodied girl accustomed to strenuous labour.	261	Una muchacha joven se encaminó hacia el estrado de los testigos<1>. Mientras levantaba la mano y juraba decir la verdad, toda la verdad y nada más que la verdad<3>, y que Dios la ayudase, su aspecto parecía un tanto frágil, pero cuando se sentó en el estrado de los testigos<4> se convirtió en lo que era: una muchacha de cuerpo macizo, acostumbrada a los trabajos penosos.
A450	538	He turned another page of the state's<1> evidence<2>, before he began reading.	556	—Buscó la página correspondiente y leyó—:

A452	538	'But in your evidence<1>, Mrs Elliot, given to Detective<2> Petrowski only moments after your husband's death, you stated<3> that you saw Ralph	--	--
L108	182	A young girl walked to the witness stand<1>. As she raised her hand and swore that the evidence<2> she gave would be the truth, the whole truth, and nothing but the truth<3> so help her God, [...].	261	Una muchacha joven se encaminó hacia el estrado de los testigos<1>. Mientras levantaba la mano y juraba decir la verdad, toda la verdad y nada más que la verdad<3>, y que Dios la ayudase [...].

Table 5. Omissions of witness, jury, courtroom, trial and evidence.

Conclusions

At the beginning of this paper I proposed two situations in which I thought the translator would use the technique of omission: abusive use by the author, or lack of cultural equivalent in the receiving culture. Now, having seen these data, we find ourselves in position of addressing them.

With regard to the first hypothesis, these data show there is not a consistent pattern between the number of appearances in the source text and the use of the technique of omission by translators. Obviously, when the repetition of a given cultural referent shows a high frequency, some omission could be expected. However, it is not consistent. As we have seen in the case of *judge* out of 109 times, there were 12 omissions and for 6 of them the translator used a mechanism of reference (surname). Let's see some more examples. If we look at the behaviour of Archer's translator, we see that *judge* is used 82 times and has been omitted 5 times, but *court* appears 34 times and is omitted 10 times. We understand this as a lack of direct correspondence between the frequency of use of a cultural referent and the use of the technique of omission. Another clear case is *courtroom*. As we have seen above, Lee is the author who uses this cultural referent the most and her translator uses translation techniques different from omission, whereas Archer and Grisham use it 19 and 18 times respectively, and their translators exclude the translation 3 times and once

respectively. Even more surprising could be the cases of *state* or *juror*. *State* is also used by all three authors, 20 times by Grisham, and all these times translated, whereas Archer used it 18 times and Lee 5, and their translators excluded its translation once each. Finally, it is interesting to mention the case of *juror* although this has not been used by all three authors. It appears 7 times in Archer's work and 34 in Grisham's, and their translators have decided to omit this cultural referent on one occasion each. As we have seen in the previous section, we can also find cases of cultural referents used only once in the whole corpus (such as *come before me*, *county solicitor*, *in open court*, *judicially*, *incarceration*) and they have been omitted. This fact confirms what we have stated above: there is a lack of direct correspondence between frequency of use of a cultural referent and the use of omission technique.

With regard to the second hypothesis, we can see, after examining the cultural referents involved, that the exclusion in the translation has not originated because of the cultural distance between the two cultures involved. A degree of cultural distance could involve a degree of difficulty or even 'impossibility' of translation due to a lack of equivalence. However, among all the omitted cultural referents, there is only one evident cultural referent that could pose this problem – *hung jury*. Interestingly enough, it has been used by all three authors appearing a total of 9 times in the whole corpus, and only once was it not translated. For the most of the cultural referents in our table, they are not a source of difficulty for the translation since there is no cultural distance or, if there is any, it can be easily overcome.

From our results, we find that the hypotheses have not been confirmed. However, this study has provided valuable results. Now, it can be claimed that the omission of cultural referents in legal fiction is not linked to the possible difficulties in finding an equivalent due to cultural distance between source text and target text or to the use/abuse of it by authors. According to these results, it can be inferred that translators have mainly decided not to translate due to either stylistic reasons, other than the redundant use of a cultural referent by the author, or other kinds of reasons (including conditions under which the translator carried out the translation).

To conclude, I would like to point out that I am aware that the corpus may seem limited, as it only consists of three novels. Nevertheless, we have to remember that

these 3 novels provided nearly 3,000 legal cultural referents. Furthermore, I believe that such a corpus can set the ground for further research – the homogeneity of topics covered by the novels makes it reasonable to consider the likeliness of similar results in a wider corpus. Obviously, the specific cultural referents that show a very limited frequency could or could not appear in other corpora. As a final comment, I believe that further research could also include a detailed study of the contexts in which cultural referents appear, to consider other possible factors that could help to explain this behaviour.

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Translation as Peaceable Resistance

Corine Tachtiris

Recent translation theory has worked to prove and promote the agency of the translator in the movement of texts from one language and culture to another. Lori Chamberlain (1988), for example, has demonstrated the many ways in which stereotypical metaphors of passivity and femininity have been used to describe translation and translators, which are thus seen as secondary to the genius of the original text and author. Drawing on the ideas of Jacques Derrida, she argues for a reassessment of the role of the translator and of the primacy of the original. Lawrence Venuti (1992, 1995) is among the forefront of those translation theorists joining Chamberlain in advancing the rights and influence of the translator. The problem with the rhetoric of scholars such as Venuti, however, is that the contested site of translation becomes a battleground, with the metaphors of passivity replaced by new metaphors of violence. I wish to propose in this paper an alternative model for thinking about the work that translators and their translations do, a model of peaceable resistance. Such a model still allows for the agency of translators and their active participation in textual and cultural practice without resorting to an economy of violence in which every change involves some sort of harm or abuse.

For the purposes of this paper, my argument centres around the decision *not* to translate, which can, of course, occur on many levels: from not translating entire texts or even sets of texts (from a certain nation, genre, political ideology, etc.) to not translating passages, sentences, or single words. In the latter case, I do not mean excision—that is, removing those words or sentences entirely from the text in the movement toward the target language—but rather not translating by leaving these in the source language in the target text. As various modes of peaceable resistance have shown, the act of not doing something has the potential to effect radical change. Labour strikes (*not* going to work) and boycotting (*not* buying something) can send powerful messages—especially when carried out on a large scale—and induce people in positions of power to alter their policies. Civil disobedience, or *not* following the rules, makes a critical comment as to the validity and justice of those rules. Thus, not doing something, rather than implying passivity, can function as a peaceable form of